

The Influence of Leadership Style and Career Development as Mediated by Work Motivation: Case of Hospital Employee Performance

Freddy Marbun¹, I Ketut R Sudiarditha², Dewi Susita³

Article history:

Received: October 23, 2022, Accepted: December, 15, 2022, Displayed Online: December, 30, 2022, Published: December, 30, 2022

Keywords

Work motivation;
Leadership style;
Career development;
Employee performance;

Abstract

This research was conducted to know the factors that can improve employee performance. It applied a survey method. The results of the study show that leadership style has no effect on the employees' work motivation, while career development and leadership style has a positive effect on the performance. In contrast, leadership style does not have a positive effect on performance through work motivation as mediation, but career development, with work motivation as a mediating variable, has a positive effect on performance for hospital employees.

1. Introduction

The hospital is a form of social health facility in the health sector that provides plenary services as well as an integrated part of the entire health care system that serves patients with various types of services. Purnami, (2017). Health services have an important role in every activity to maintain and improve the health or standard of living of the community, which aims to achieve optimal health in hospitals and quality resources for the community. In the development of the health service business world in the recent era of globalization, it has continued to increase both in quality and quantity. To improve the quality and quantity of hospital services also requires a management system that can mobilize all existing human resources so that it will have an impact on achieving performance. Setyawan and Supriyanto, (2020).

Achievement of performance in an organization is highly dependent on the quality of its human resources. The quality of human resources is needed where the higher the resources owned, the

¹State University of Jakarta, Jakarta, Indonesia. Email: freddymarbun27@gmail.com

²State University of Jakarta, Jakarta, Indonesia Email: ketut.sudiarditha@unj.ac.id

³State University of Jakarta, Jakarta, Indonesia Email : dewisusita_man@unj.ac.id

higher the performance in an organization. Organizations or companies really need human resources in achieving its goals. Organizational upheaval that is so fast from year to year requires high-performance human resources supported by knowledge, skills and behavior to improve the performance of an organization Gede et al. (2017).

Human resource issues are currently still the center of attention, policies, practices and foundation for an organization to survive in the era of globalization which is accompanied by an increasingly fierce level of competition (Dessler, 2011). Even though it is supported by facilities and infrastructure and sources of funds, without the support of reliable human resources, organizational activities will not be completed properly Widodo, (2012); Gede et al. (2017).

Hospital "XYZ" as one of the private hospitals in East Jakarta which is engaged in health services which has tough challenges in dealing with other health service providers, where one form of social service facilities and public services in the field of health services is of course must provide the best service and quality (Purnami, 2017). However, the hospital as an organizational vessel must have an open system and always interact with the environment to achieve dynamic balance Primanita et al., (2018)

Based on the type of private general hospital in East Jakarta, RS. "XYZ" has type C which means level two health facilities that accommodate referral services from clinics and puskesmas which are limited in nature. Hospital as a public facility which is a health service center must be able to improve health services in an integrated manner according to the classification and type of hospital.

Table 1.
Type C Private General Hospital for the East Jakarta Region in 2021

No.	General Hospital Name	Category
1	Harapan Jayakarta Hospital	Type C
2	Harum Sisma Medika Hospital	Type C
3	hospital El-Shama	Type C
4	Kartika Pulo Mas Hospital	Type C
5	Mediros Hospital	Type C
6	Restu Kasih Hospital	Type C
7	Yadika Hospital	Type C
8	Admiral Hospital	Type C
9	Rawamangun Surgical Hospital	Type C
10	Bina Waluyo Hospital	Type C
11	RS Dr. Euis	Type C
12	Kelender Islamic Hospital	Type C
13	Sayyida Hospital	Type C
14	Sammria Basra Hospital	Type C
15	Alvemias Agusta Hospital	Type C

Source: bpsdmdk.kemkes.go.id (February, 2022)

Based on the performance assessment of public service units carried out based on Permen PAN-RB No.17 of 2017, namely:

Table 2 .
Public Service Unit Performance Assessment

No.	Rated aspect	Weight
1	Service Policy	30%
2	HR professionalism	18%
3	Facilities and infrastructure	15%
4	Public Service Information System (SIPP)	15%
5	Consultations and Complaints	15%
6	Innovation	7%
Total		100%

Source:www.mempan.go.id (February 2022)

It can be seen from the assessment criteria, that the professionalism of human resources (HR) ranks 2nd in the weight of performance evaluation so that hospitals as health care institutions must be wise in designing strategies in terms of facilities, infrastructure and human resources. Along with the development of technological advances, the influence of globalization, the increasingly high level of competition, the behavior of patients who are increasingly observant and critical in choosing health services has become a trigger for hospitals to always provide optimal service to the community.

Based on the employee performance report at the "XYZ" hospital, it was also seen a decrease in employee performance. Employee performance indicators as a measure of performance achievement are the extent to which employees provide optimal results (Robbins, 2015). As for the performance appraisal data we got from the staffing department of the hospital. "XYZ" is as follows:

Table 3.
Hospital Employee Performance Assessment Level In 2019-2021

No	Part	Performance Indicators								
		Responsibility			Motivation			Performance		
		20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20
		19	20	21	19	20	21	19	20	21
1	Staffing	85	80	75	80	70	70	75	70	69
2	Training	80	75	70	80	70	70	75	70	69
3	Finance	85	75	70	80	70	70	75	70	69
4	Cashier counter / insurance cashier	80	75	70	80	70	70	75	70	67
5	Registration & Information	80	75	70	80	70	65	75	70	67
6	Secretariat	80	75	70	80	70	70	75	70	67
7	Household & general	85	75	70	80	70	65	75	70	69
8	Outpatient Poly Admin	85	75	70	80	70	70	75	70	67

9	Inpatient Admin	80	75	70	80	70	70	75	70	67
10	Laboratory Administration	80	75	70	80	70	70	75	70	67
11	Admin of Medical Records	80	75	70	80	70	70	75	70	67
12	Medical Rehab Admin	80	75	70	80	70	70	75	70	69
13	Nutrition Admin	85	75	70	80	70	65	75	70	67
14	Admin Ipsrs	80	75	70	80	70	75	75	70	67
15	Emergency Installation Admin	85	75	70	80	70	70	75	70	67
16	Driver/courier	85	75	70	80	70	65	75	70	69

Source: RS.XYZ Personnel Data (February 2022)

Value Description:

Not enough : < 60

Enough : 61-75

Well : > 76

Based on Table 3. The level of employee performance appraisal at the "XYZ"-Jakarta Hospital for 2019-2021 shows that employee performance indicators have decreased. The decline in performance indicators occurred in the indicators: responsibility, motivation, and performance. Based on these data it can be seen that every year the performance of hospital employees experiences a decrease in employee performance which is influenced by one of them is the employee motivation factor. Employee motivation is very important in supporting performance, because motivation is an encouragement or motivating someone to work better. Employees who are dissatisfied with their jobs can be motivated to work better (Armstrong, M. and Baron, 2007).

Several previous relevant studies, including research by Abdullah et al., (2013) reported the work motivation of employees at Level III Ambon Hospital which was in the low category of 64.29%. The same research conducted by Budiawan (2015) also showed very low work motivation of 60.1% at the Bali Mental Hospital. The results of different studies are reported (Princess and Rosa, 2015) in the inpatient room of the PKU Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta Unit II hospital where the proportion of low work motivation is less, namely only 13.80%. The research above gives the meaning that work motivation in each hospital is different, this depends on the factors that influence it. Based on the description above, it can be said that employee motivation can be a factor that brings success and supports performance in an organization, which means that employees have a positive attitude towards the organization, it is necessary to create and maintain good working conditions.

In addition to the above factors that can affect employee performance is leadership style which is no less important in improving employee performance is leadership style Purnomo et al., (2020); Ali, (2016). Leadership itself is a pattern of behavior that is displayed as a leader, where when the leader tries to influence the behavior of others. Meanwhile according to Hasibuan, (2016) that leadership style is a way for leaders to influence their subordinates to want to work together and work productively to achieve organizational goals. Because the behavior shown by subordinates is basically the response of subordinates to the leadership style carried out by them (Ali and Agustian, 2018). So based on the opinion of several experts regarding leadership style, it can be concluded that

how superiors/leaders influence their subordinates to work productively to achieve organizational goals.

Based on the literature from several previous studies, that apart from leadership style there are other factors that affect performance, one of which is career development, where career development felt by every employee at work is the process of increasing an employee's work ability and encouraging increased performance in order to achieve a better career. wanted. Career development supported by the company expects feedback from employees in the form of good performance. As stated by Dessler (2013), any procedure that includes setting career development standards at work and then assessing employees' actual performance to be matched with predetermined performance standards.

Career development is also one of the factors that affect employee performance, where career development is a series of positions and positions occupied by someone during their work period through training in an organizational environment. Syahputra and Tanjung, (2020). Career development as one of the human resource management activities basically has a goal that can improve and increase the effectiveness of the implementation of work by employees so that they are able to contribute to the achievement of company goals. Career development is basically oriented towards company or organizational development in this case as an employee activity to plan a future career in the workplace (Arismunandar and Khair, 2020). Career development also gives employees the opportunity to meet with various parties, both internal and external to the company or organization to plan their careers. Therefore an employee is a person who is most interested in the process of career development activities.

To ascertain whether the causal factors that can affect the performance of "XYZ" Hospital employees mentioned in the background above are truly behavioral factors of employee performance, the researchers then conducted a pre-survey of 20 employees with the following results:

Table 4. Research Pre-Survey Results

No.	Variable	Statement	Yes	Not
1	Leadership Style	Performance is influenced by the existing leadership style	13	7
2	Career development	Performance is influenced by the existence of career opportunities provided by the company	8	12
3	Motivation	Performance is influenced by motivation that is in me internally	9	11
4	Compensation	Performance is affected by the high compensation given	6	12
5	Work environment	Performance is influenced by the availability of a good work environment	4	16
6	Competence	Performance is influenced by the level of competence that I have	6	12

Source: Data processed by Researchers (2022)

Table 4. shows that the results of the pre-survey with a sample of 20 respondents found that there were 3 main determining factors in increasing employee performance, namely Leadership Style, Career Development and Motivation respectively 13 people, 8 people and 9 people.

In general, the findings in the pre-survey above confirm previous research journals conducted by Hersugondo, (2008) states that effective leadership and organizational change is leadership that plays an important role in an organization. In conditions like this a leader must be able to adjust to changes that are successful or not, much is determined by a company leader. A leader is someone who has the authority to govern other people and in carrying out his work to achieve the goals set with the help of others. Research conducted by Sicily, (2015) concluded that leadership factors do not affect employee job satisfaction but simultaneously. Leadership, career development and motivation factors influence employee job satisfaction.(Muhlis, 2016) the research results show that leadership and career development simultaneously have a positive and significant effect on employee performance; leaders who partially have a positive and significant influence on employee performance; Career development partially has a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

In particular, this research wants to know the factors that can improve employee performance. Based on empirical studies conducted by researchers collected from previous research related to factors that influence performance, including by Purnomo et al., (2020); Ali, (2016) states that leadership style influences performance;Silaban et al., (2021);Yusuf and Thoyib, (2021);Dian and Safitri, (2018);Natalia and netra, (2020) stating that career development has an effect on performance;Fonseca and Costa, (2020); Altheeb, (2020); Dian and Safitri, (2018) states that motivation influences performance.

2. Materials and Methods

This study applied a survey method and is based on explanations Sugiyono, (2017) the survey method is a writing method that is carried out on large and small populations, but the data studied is data from samples taken from the population, so that relative events, distribution and relationships between variables are found. The writing method used in this paper is a survey method with a correlational approach and involves the dependent variable. The variables of this study consist of four variables, namely leadership style and career development which are independent variables which are depicted by symbols X1 and X2 respectively, and work motivation which are intervening or connecting variables which are depicted by symbols Y, and employee performance is the dependent variable. with the symbol (Z) with the resulting behavior for the independent and intervening variables.

3. Results and Discussions

The Effect of Leadership Style on Work Motivation

In the leadership style variable, the factor loading value of the highest indicator is obtained with the indicator code GK7 having a factor coding value of 0.915. This finding indicates that the GK7 indicator or the questionnaire statement is "free of opinion". From the results of this research, it can be concluded that in general, respondents pay special attention to the "free opinion" indicator, this is natural because they, as employees, also have rights that must be fulfilled by the leadership of the organization. Whereas in the work motivation variable, the indicator that has the highest factor loading is the MK8 code with the sound of the questionnaire statement saying "Employees can quickly adjust to work. One of the motivations from within employees is their speed in adapting to new

*The Influence of Leadership Style and Career Development as Mediated
by Work Motivation: Case of Hospital Employee Performance
(Freddy Marbun, I Ketut R. Sudiarditha, Dewi Susita)*

environments. The work environment must provide comfort to employees, especially new employees.

Previous research conducted by Dewi, (2019) and Dewi and Utama, (2016) that there is no influence of leadership style on employee motivation, meaning that employee motivation will increase if leaders in the organization change their leadership style, the point is that if the leadership style is applied correctly and appropriately, it will be able to direct the achievement of organizational and individual goals. Conversely, if the leadership style chosen is wrong and not in accordance with the existing situation, it will result in difficulty achieving organizational goals. This will have an impact on increasing the human resources in the company, so that even those employees who are working will be very enthusiastic and motivated in the future. Based on this description, the results of this study are relevant to the results of research conducted by Fiaz et al., (2017);Mesaak, (2020);Dewi, (2019), ;Widodo, (2021);Dewi & Utama, (2016);Altheeb, (2020).

Effect of career development on work motivation

In the career development variable, there is an indicator that has the highest factor loading value, namely an indicator with a PK6 code of 0.897, with a questionnaire statement saying "kEmployees are conscientious in carrying out their work. This statement provides an understanding that if employees want good career development, one of the indicators that will be assessed is thoroughness, employees are thorough in carrying out their work. Whereas in the work motivation variable, the indicator that has the highest factor loading is the MK8 code with the sound of the questionnaire statement saying "employees can quickly adjust to work". One of the motivations from within employees is their speed in adapting to new environments. The work environment must provide comfort to employees, especially new employees. Leaders must pay attention to employees, by providing training so that employees can quickly innovate with their work.

From the results of the research above, employees of the "XYZ" Hospital should always try to complete work on time, apart from being the responsibility of an employee. Leaders should properly provide targets and motivation for employees to complete tasks on time, this will affect the career development of "XYZ" Hospital employees. The leadership of the "XYZ" Hospital has the authority to select employees who are considered good and meet the criteria for obtaining career development based on experience, as well as higher education, complying with the regulations set by the company, not committing serious violations and so on.

Based on this description, the results of this study are relevant to the results of research conducted byAltheeb, (2020),Prayogi and Lesmana, (2021),Saleem and Amin, (2013),Silaban et al., (2021),Ramli and Yudhistira, (2018),Zainal and Rivai, (2014),Dialoke and Nkechi, (2017),Zarei et al., (2016),Li et al., (2014),Afolab et al., (2018).

The influence of leadership style on employee performance

In the leadership style variable, the factor loading value of the highest indicator is obtained with the indicator code GK7 having a factor coding value of 0.915. This finding indicates that the GK7 indicator or the questionnaire statement is "free of opinion". From the results of this research, it can be concluded that in general, respondents pay special attention to the "free opinion" indicator, this is natural because they, as employees, also have rights that must be fulfilled by the leadership of the organization. Whereas in the employee performance variable, the performance indicator that has the highest factor loading is the KK7 code with the sound of the questionnaire statement saying "Employees provide ideas/ideas to the leadership for the progress of the hospital. Ideas and ideas from members of the organization are needed by the leadership of the organization for the progress

of the organization. One form of support and involvement of an employee in the organization is to provide ideas for the progress of the organization.

A leader must know the good or bad performance of employees so that the organization has suggestions and solutions in dealing with crises in the future. Often these problems cause deep bad organizational impressions due to ignoring warning signs of declining employee performance. One of the solutions to improve employee performance is that in the recruitment process employees must meet certain criteria according to the position in the company by paying attention to educational graduates, skills, and employee skills. Besides that, the attitude of the employees themselves. Thus, it is expected that employees who meet these criteria can certainly be placed in positions that are in accordance with their expertise, namely applying the principle of "the right man in the right place".

Based on this description, the results of this study are relevant to the results of previous research conducted by Purnomo et al., (2020), Iqbal et al., (2015), Shafie et al., (2013), Aisha, (2020), Khudhair et al., (2022), Ojokuku et al., (2012), Naderi and Jadidi, (2014), Du Plessis and Cole, (2011)

The influence of career development on employee performance

In the career development variable, there is an indicator that has the highest factor loading value, namely an indicator with a PK6 code of 0.897, with a questionnaire statement saying "Employees are conscientious in carrying out their work. This statement provides an understanding that if employees want good career development, one of the indicators that will be assessed is thoroughness, employees are thorough in carrying out their work. The performance variable that has the highest factor loading is the KK7 code with the statement on the questionnaire reading "employees provide ideas/ideas to the leadership for the progress of the hospital". Ideas and ideas from members of the organization are needed by the leadership of the organization for the progress of the organization. One form of support and involvement of an employee in the organization is to provide ideas for the progress of the organization.

Based on the age criteria at the XYZ hospital with a sample of 110 respondents, it can be seen that the presentation of productive age, namely 31-40 years, and working experience of 1-5 years worked the longest at the XYZ hospital and was dominated by married respondents. It can also be seen that new employees who have worked for 5 years are still enthusiastic at work and are able to adapt quickly to a new work environment. In improving skills and competencies there needs to be clear career development so as to be able to boost employee performance so that employees feel comfortable working because there is career development that every employee looks forward to.

Based on this description, the results of this study are relevant to the results of research conducted by Niati et al., (2021), Muhammad, (2019), Arifin et al., (2020), Setiyaningrum, (2019), Mark and Nzulwa, (2018), Ombui, (2021), Obuba and Hello, (2021).

Effect of work motivation on employee performance

Work motivation variable, the indicator that has the highest factor loading is the MK8 code with the sound of the questionnaire statement saying "Employees can quickly adjust to work. One of the motivations from within employees is their speed in adapting to new environments. The work environment must provide comfort to employees, especially new employees. Leaders must pay attention to employees, by providing training so that employees can quickly innovate with their work. While the performance variable that has the highest factor loading is code KK7 with the statement on the questionnaire reading "employees provide ideas/ideas to the leadership for the progress of the

hospital". Ideas and ideas from members of the organization are needed by the leadership of the organization for the progress of the organization.

In line with the research conducted by Kadarisman, (2012) that motivation is also to: (1) Change employee behavior, (2) Increase passion and morale, (3) Increase work discipline, (4) Increase work performance, (5) Increase sense of responsibility, (6) Increase productivity and employee performance efficiency, and (7) Fostering employee loyalty to a company or organization. Motivation can also be in the form of material or motivation in the form of an expression of gratitude for the hard work that has been given to achieve good organizational performance.

Hospital "XYZ" if you want to succeed or achieve predetermined goals by improving employee performance. The success of the company depends on the behavior of employees to be able to achieve goals effectively and efficiently. An organization must treat employees humanely, namely by providing work that can enhance their dignity, provide the necessary facilities, meet expectations, provide motivation, provide opportunities to grow and develop and provide health and safety guarantees. This condition is absolutely necessary if employees feel their needs and expectations are fulfilled, they will certainly be more loyal in devoting themselves fully to the goals and objectives of the company or organization by themselves.

Based on this description, the results of this research are relevant to the results of research conducted by Purnomo et al., (2020), Fiaz et al., (2017), Altheeb, (2020), Jaya et al., (2020), Prayogi and Lesmana, (2021), Yusuf and Thoyib, (2021), Rajhans, (2012), Okoth and Oluoch, (2019), Matsie, (2008), Abusharbeh and Nazzal, (2018), Deressa and Zeru, (2019).

The indirect effect of leadership style on employee performance is mediated by work motivation

Based on the results of this study indicate that the leadership style applied at the "XYZ" Hospital can affect the level of employee performance through employee motivation. In a sense, that the variable of work motivation cannot influence significantly in mediating the relationship between leadership style and employee performance. By changing the pattern of leadership style at the XYZ hospital, it is likely that it will increase the performance of employees who are given strong encouragement and motivation, most likely to be motivated to increase work productivity.

Research conducted by Pramudjadi, (2012) who said that where leadership power does not have a significant positive effect on employee performance which is mediated by motivation. This means that motivation cannot mediate the effect of leadership style on employee performance. The existence of a leadership style greatly affects a person's performance at work and in the completion of each job, it can be said that leaders have traits and characters that are not liked by employees or subordinates, so it will have a negative impact on the progress of a company or organization. Based on this description, the research results are relevant to the research conducted by Sari, (2022), Diniaty et al., (2014), Widodo, (2021), Pawirosumarto, (2017), Fonseca and Costa, (2020).

The indirect effect of career development on employee performance is mediated by work motivation

According to previous research conducted by Prayogi and Lesmana, (2021) which stated that work motivation has a positive and significant effect in mediating the effect of career development on employee performance. In addition, according to research Kuranchie-Mensah, and Tawiah, (2016) state work motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance, meaning that work motivation has a positive and significant effect in mediating the relationship between career development and employee performance.

Based on the description above, the results of this study are relevant to the results of research conducted by Natalia Netra, (2020), Kuranchie-Mensah, and Tawiah, (2016), Prayogi and Lesmana, (2021), Sapta and Sudja, (2018), (Saleem and Amin, (2013), Sakti and Kurniawan, (2022).

4. Conclusion

Based on the results of research and testing in the discussion put forward, several conclusions can be drawn as follows.

1. Leadership style has no effect on the work motivation of "XYZ" hospital employees. This means that the higher the leadership style, the employee motivation will decrease.
2. Career development has a positive effect on the work motivation of "XYZ" hospital employees. This means that the higher the career development, the work motivation will increase.
3. Leadership style has a positive effect on the performance of "XYZ" hospital employees. This means that the higher the leadership style, the performance will increase.
4. Career development has a positive effect on the performance of "XYZ" hospital employees. This means that the higher the career development, the employee's performance will increase.
5. Work motivation has a positive and significant effect on the performance of "XYZ" hospital employees. This means that the higher the work motivation, the employee's performance will increase.
6. Leadership style has no positive effect on performance through work motivation as a mediation for "XYZ" hospital employees. This means that the higher the leadership style, the impact on employee performance will decrease and not be optimal through the provision of appropriate work motivation to employee performance.
7. Career development has a positive effect on performance with work motivation as a mediating variable for "XYZ" hospital employees. This means that the higher the career development, the impact on employee performance will increase and it will be more optimal if it is through the provision of work motivation to employees. This means that by running a good employee career development program, it can motivate employees to be more active and good at work and employees work better too, so their performance will automatically increase.

Acknowledgments

First of all, the authors express their gratitude to God the Almighty because it is only by His grace that this manuscript can be completed. Next, the authors wish to express their sincere gratitude to the publisher of TIJOSSW, who gave permission and a great chance for the Authors to publish their writings. The next appreciation is given to the reviewers of the TIJOSSW publisher who has spent more time making valuable corrections dealing with technical writing styles or ideas about this writing.

References

- Abdullah, AZ, Hamzah, A., & Mulyono, MH (2013). Factors Influencing Nurse Performance in Level III Hospital 16.06. 01 Ambon. *Indonesian Journal of Health Administration and Policy*, 2(01), 8270.
- Abusharbeh, MT, & Nazzal, HH (2018). The impact of motivations on employee performance: a case study from Palestinian commercial banks. *International Business Research*, 11(4), 142–153.
- Ali, K., & Agustian, and DW (2018). Analysis of the Influence of Organizational Culture and Leadership Style on Job Satisfaction to Improve Employee Performance at Muhammadiyah Metro Hospital. *FE-UMM Scientific Journal*, 12(2).
- Altheeb, S.A. (2020). Leadership Style and Employee Motivation : A Study of Saudi Arabian Work Environment *Estilo de liderazgo y motivacion de los employees : un estudio del ambiente de trabajo de Arabia Saudita*. 8(2).
- Arifin, AH, & Raza, Hendra, Jumadil Saputra, AP (2020). The Influence Of Recruitment And Career Development Towards Employee Performance : A Mediating Role Of Competence. October.
- Arismunandar, MF, & Khair, H. (2020). The Effect of Compensation, Position Analysis and Patterns of Career Development on Employee Performance. *Maneggio*:
- Armstrong, M. and Baron, A. (1998). *Performance Management – The New Realities*. London: Institute of Personnel and Development. Institute of Personnel and Development.
- Chung, HFL, Wang, CL, Huang, PH, & Yang, Z. (2016). Organizational capabilities and business performance: When and how does the dark side of managerial ties matter? *Industrial Marketing Management*, 55, 70–82. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indmarman.2016.02.014>
- Deressa, AT, & Zeru, G. (2019). Work motivation and its effects on organizational performance: the case of nurses in Hawassa public and private hospitals: Mixed method study approach. *BMC Research Notes*, 12(1), 1–6.
- Dessler, G. (2010). *Human Resource Management*, 10th edition volume 1, Jakarta: PT. Index.
- Dessler, G. (2011). *Human Resource Management*. Index Publisher, Jakarta. Index Publisher, Jakarta.
- Dessler, G. (2012). *Personnel Management*, Erlangga Publisher, Jakarta. Erlangga Publisher, Jakarta.
- Dewi, NN (2019). Analysis of the Effect of Leadership Style and Work Environment on Employee Performance Using Work Motivation as an Intervening Variable: (Case Study at PT. SUPARMA Tbk). *Media Mahardhika*, 17(2), 278–288.
- Dialoke, I., & Nkechi, PAJ (2017). Effects of career growth on employee performance: A study of non-academic staff of Michael Okpara University of Agriculture Umudike Abia State, Nigeria. *Singaporean Journal of Business Economics, and Management Studies (SJBEM)*, 5(7), 8–18.
- Diniaty, D., Fairus, M., Industry, JT, Islam, U., Sultan, N., & Kasim, S. (2014). Analysis of Factors Influencing the Performance of Library Staff of UIN Suska Riau. *Journal of Science, Technology and Industry*, 11(2), 297–304. <https://doi.org/ISSN 1693-2390 print/ISSN 2407-0939 online ANALYSIS>
- Du Plessis, C., & Cole, RJ (2011). Motivating change: Shifting the paradigm. *Building Research and Information*, 39(5), 436–449. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09613218.2011.582697>
- Erri, D., Lestari, AP, & Asymar, HH (2021). The Effect of Leadership Style on Employee Performance at Pt Melzer Global Sejahtera Jakarta. *Journal of Research Innovation*, 1(9), 1897–1906.
- Feldman, DC, & Hugh, JA (2003). *Management Industrial and Group Behavior in Organizations*. New York McGraw-Hill Book Company.
- Ferdinand, A. (2014). *BP Management Research Method*, Diponegoro University. Semarang.
- Fiaz, M., Su, Q., & Ikram, A. (2017). Leadership styles and employees' motivation : Perspective from an emerging economy *Leadership Styles And Employees' Motivation : Perspective From An Emerging*. June 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1353/jda.2017.0093>
- Fonseca, L., & Costa, D. (2020). The role of work motivation as a mediator on the influence of

- education-training and leadership style on employee performance. 10, 1497–1504. <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.msl.2019.12.017>
- Gede, ID, Putra, D., & Utama, IWM (2017). The Effect of Work Environment and Job Satisfaction on Turnover Intention at Mayaloka Villas Seminyak. *Unud Management E-Journal*, Vol. 6, No. 9, 2017: 5116-5143, 6(9), 5116–5143.
- Hasibuan, M. (2016). *Human Resource Management*. Jakarta: Bumi Aksara Publisher. Jakarta: Bumi Aksara Publisher.
- Iqbal, N., Anwar, S., & Haider, N. (2015). Effect of leadership style on employee performance. *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review*, 5(5), 1–
- Jaya, AD, Ramly, M., Sinring, B., & Sukmawati, S. (2020). Influence of competence and motivation, on job satisfaction and employee performance at Makassar Bhayangkara Hospital. *Journal of Business and Management*, 22(7), 28–34.
- Khudhair, FS, Rahman, RA, Adnan, AABZ, & Khudhair, AA (2022). Impact of Leadership Style on Employee Performance (A Case Study on a Private Organization in Iraq). *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 13, 15–32.
- Li, L., Hu, H., Zhou, H., He, C., Fan, L., Liu, X., Zhang, Z., Li, H., & Sun, T. (2014). Work stress, work motivation and their effects on job satisfaction in community health workers: a cross-sectional survey in China. *BMJ Open*, 4(6), e004897.
- Mark, L., & Nzulwa, J. (2018). Effect of career development programs on employee performance in kenya. a case of national hospital insurance fund. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Information Technology*, IV, 693–709.
- Mendrofa, SS (2021). The Effect of Leadership Style on Employee Work Motivation at the South Nias Regency Food Security Service. *South Nias Student Scientific Journal*, 4(2).
- Mesaak, E. (2020). The Effect of Leadership Style on Employee Work Motivation at the District Office of Tutuk Tolu District, East Seram Regency. *IAIN Ambon*.
- Muhlis, M. (2016). The Effect of Leadership and Career Development on Employee Performance at Pt. Suzuki Finance Indonesia Palu. *Catalogist*, 4(10).
- Naderi, N., & Jadidi, L. (2014). The Study of the effects between Leadership Style, Organization Culture, Employees Performance on Leadership Performance (Case: Government Hospitals in Isfahan). *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 4(12), 187.
- Natalia, NKSS, & Netra, IGSK (2020). The Effect of Work Motivation in Mediating the Effect of Career Development on Performance. *E-Journal of Management*, Vol. 9, No. 4, 9(4), 1507–1526.
- Obuba, R., & Hallo, AH (2021). Assessment of Career Development on Employee Performance in Private Health Sector in Isiolo County. *Asian Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting*, 1–10.
- Ojokuku, RM, Odetayo, TA, & Sajuyigbe, USA (2012). Impact of leadership style on organizational performance: a case study of Nigerian banks. *American Journal of Business and Management*, 1(4), 202–207.
- Prayogi, MA, & Lesmana, MT (2021). The Influence of Leadership Style and Motivation on the Performance of Employees. 161(Ciiber 2019), 122–127.
- Primanita, D., Widyanty, W., & Aditya, F. (2018). The Influence of Competence, Organizational Culture and Motivation on Regional Public Hospital Employee Performance. *Scientific Journal of Business Management*, 4(2), 152–171.
- Purnami, PR (2017b). The Influence of Compensation and Perceptions of Organizational Support on Organizational Commitment and Employee Performance at the Balimed Karangasem Hospital. *JAGADHITA:Journal of Economics & Business*, Vol. 4, No 1. March 2017, pp 95-107, 4(1), 95–107.

The Influence of Leadership Style and Career Development as Mediated by Work Motivation: Case of Hospital Employee Performance (Freddy Marbun, I Ketut R. Sudiarditha, Dewi Susita)

- <https://doi.org/10.22225/JJ.4.1.226.95-107>
- Purnomo, BR, Eliyana, A., & Pramesti, ED (2020). The Effect of Leadership Style, Organizational Culture and Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance with Organizational Commitment as the Intervening Variable. 11(10), 446–458.
- Putri, IRR, & Rosa, EM (2015). Analysis of the work motivation of nurses in the inpatient room of PKU Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta Unit II Hospital. JNKI (Jurnal of Nurses and Midwifery Indonesia)(Indonesian Journal of Nursing and Midwifery), 3(2), 82–90.
- Rajhans, K. (2012). Effective organizational communication: A key to employee motivation and performance. *Interscience Management Review*, 2(2), 81–85.
- Ramli, AH, & Yudhistira, R. (2018). The Effect of Career Development on Employee Performance through Organizational Commitment at PT. Infomedia Humanika Solutions in Jakarta. 4th National Scholars Seminar 2018 ISSN (F): 2460 - 8696. National Scholars Seminar, 4.
- Robbins, S. (2015). *Organizational behavior*. Salemba Empat Jakarta.
- Sakti, DD, & Kurniawan, D. (2022). The Importance Of Competence And Career Development Towards Employee Performance In Mediation Of Motivation Variables In Bi Money Management Work Units (Satker) In Java Island. *Dynasty International Journal of Digital Business Management*, 3(5), 723–731.
- Saleem, S., & Amin, S. (2013). The impact of organizational support for career development and supervisory support on employee performance: An empirical study from the Pakistani academic sector. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 5(5), 194–207.
- Sapta, IKS, & Sudja, IN (2018). The Effect of Career Development and Leadership on Employee Performance with Work Motivation as Intervening Variables on Cv . Blue Waters Bali. 9(5), 20583–20591.
- Saputra, W. and IW (2017). The Effect of Leadership Style on Employee Performance Through Discipline and Work Motivation of PPSU Employees in Duren Sawit Village, East Jakarta. 5(2), 1–19.
- Saragih, Bongsu, Anwar Sanusi, and A., & Manan. (2017). The Influence of Job Satisfaction towards Employee Performance on the Antecedents of Competencies and Organizational Citizenship Behavior.” *IOSR Journal of Business and Management* 19(01):21–27. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*, 19(1), 21–27.
- Sari, J. (2022). The Effect of Leadership Style on Performance: Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable. 1(1), 43–64.
- Setiyaningrum, AC (2019). Career Development on Employee Performance Through Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable. *Journal of Management Science*, 7(3), 824–831.
- Setyawan, FEB, & Supriyanto, S. (2020). *Hospital management*. Zifatama Jawa.
- Shafie, B., Baghersalimi, S., & Barghi, V. (2013). The relationship between leadership style and employee performance: Case study of real estate registration organization of Tehran Province. *Singaporean Journal of Business, Economics and Management Studies*, 51(1119), 1–9.
- Sicilia, G. (2015). The Influence of Leadership, Career Development and Motivation on Job Satisfaction of Bank Riau Kepri Main Branch Pekanbaru Employees. *Tepak Journal of Business Management*, 7(1), 62–75.
- Silaban, RL, Handaru, AW, & Saptono, A. (2021). Effect of Workload , Competency , and Career Development on Employee Performance with Organizational Commitment Intervening Variables. 3(1), 294–311.
- Sugiyono. (2017). *Quantitative Research Methods, Qualitative, and R&D*. Alfabeta, Bandung.
- Wibowo, M.Si, I., & Saputra, W. (2017). The Influence of Leadership Style on Employee Performance Through Discipline and Work Motivation of Ppsu Employees, Duren Sawit Village, East Jakarta.